

Table S1

Table S1: Studies on emergency construction management

Perspective	Study	Author (Year)	Publication	Methodology or framework	Research content of study
Resource allocation and optimization	Deria et al. (2024); Liu et al. (2023); Teng et al. (2023); Ghannad et al. (2020); El-Anwar et al. (2016); Orabi et al. (2010); El-Anwar et al. (2009)	Deria et al. (2024)	Journal of Management in Engineering	Deep reinforcement learning	Creates a real-time system for optimizing the allocation of prefabricated housing modules
		Liu et al. (2023)	Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management	GIS technique and genetic algorithms	Develops a site selection model for quickly determining the best locations to build emergency medical facilities
		Teng et al. (2023)	Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management	Cloud model evaluation method	Develops a sustainability framework for deciding how to renovate and reuse temporary emergency medical buildings after a crisis
		Ghannad et al. (2020)	Journal of Management in Engineering	Genetic algorithm and analytic hierarchy process	Establishes a model to prioritize the reconstruction of damaged facilities by maximizing socio-economic benefits
		Orabi et al. (2010)	Journal of Management in Engineering	Multi-objective genetic algorithm NSGA-II	Presents a framework for allocating limited post-disaster reconstruction resources among competing projects to find the best trade-offs between time and cost
Innovative technology & construction methods	Kucan et al. (2024); Zhou et al. (2024); Tao et al. (2023); Maracchini et al. (2022); Tan et al. (2021); Chen et al. (2021); Wang et al. (2015); Chen et al. (2011)	Kucan et al. (2024)	Journal of Management in Engineering	Innovative design approach	Proposes a design approach to create modular and adaptable hospitals that can easily switch between normal and emergency functions

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Table S1 (continued)

Perspective	Study	Author (Year)	Publication	Methodology or framework	Research content of study
		Zhou et al. (2024)	Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management	Generative design and optimization	Proposes an approach using generative design to automatically create optimized hospital layouts that are effective in both normal and pandemic modes
		Tao et al. (2023)	Automation in Construction	Blockchain framework	Develops a blockchain system to secure data and improve collaboration during the rapid design phases of emergency projects
		Maracchini et al. (2022)	Building and Environment	Innovative design approach	Analyzes the performance of a lightweight emergency construction system to improve indoor comfort
		Chen et al. (2021)	Automation in Construction	Case study approach	Presents a case study of Leishenshan Hospital to demonstrate how technologies like BIM, drones, and big data were integrated for rapid construction
Organizational management	Xie et al. (2025); Ying et al. (2025); Tan et al. (2024); Lu et al. (2023); Jiang et al. (2023); Wang et al. (2023a); Yang et al. (2023); Wang et al. (2021)	Xie et al. (2025)	Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management	Structural equation model	Explores how the act of improvising with limited resources in an emergency fosters the innovation needed to solve unexpected problems
		Ying et al. (2025)	Journal of Construction Engineering and Management	Case study approach	Develops and validates a theoretical model explaining how resourceful improvisation enables the rapid completion of emergency projects
		Tan et al. (2024)	Journal of Management in Engineering	Case study approach	Shows how integrating modularity across the product, process, and organization was essential for managing complexity in the Huoshenshan Hospital
		Jiang et al. (2023)	Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management	Combination of qualitative and quantitative methods	Applies lean construction principles to workforce management during a pandemic to improve both emergency response and productivity
		Wang et al. (2023a)	Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management	Social network analysis	Proposes and analyzes a collaborative model of all project stakeholders to explain the success of hyper-fast projects

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Table S1 (continued)

Perspective	Study	Author (Year)	Publication	Methodology framework	or	Research content of study
		Wang et al. (2021)	Journal of Management in Engineering	Structural model	equation	Investigates the psychological factors that motivate construction participants to go above and beyond their duties on emergency projects

References of Table S1

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S2. Proofs and derivations

Proof of Proposition 1

According to Forster (1982), for infinite-horizon problems with time delays in both the control input and the state variable:

$$\max_{u(t)} \int_{t_0}^{\infty} f(t, x(t), u(t)) dt \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dx(t)}{dt} = g(t, x(t), x(t - \tau), u(t), u(t - \tau)) \quad (2)$$

$$x(t) = x_0, \quad t \in [-\tau, 0] \quad (3)$$

$$u(t) = u_0, \quad t \in [-\tau, 0] \quad (4)$$

The necessary conditions for optimality are:

$$\begin{cases} t \in [t_0, \infty) : \frac{\partial H(t)}{\partial u(t)} + \frac{\partial H(t + \tau)}{\partial u(t)} = 0 & \text{or} & \left. \frac{\partial H(t)}{\partial u(t)} + \frac{\partial H(t)}{\partial u(t - \tau)} \right|_{t+\tau} = 0 \\ t \in [t_0, \infty) : -\dot{\lambda}(t) = \frac{\partial H(t)}{\partial x(t)} + \frac{\partial H(t + \tau)}{\partial x(t)} & \text{or} & -\dot{\lambda}(t) = \frac{\partial H(t)}{\partial x(t)} + \frac{\partial H(t)}{\partial x(t - \tau)} \Big|_{t+\tau} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{cases} H(t) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} f(t, x(t), u(t)) + \lambda(t)g(t, x(t), x(t - \tau), u(t), u(t - \tau)) \\ H(t + \tau) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} f(t + \tau, x(t + \tau), u(t + \tau)) + \lambda(t + \tau)g(t, x(t + \tau), x(t), u(t + \tau), u(t)) \\ H(t + \tau) = H(t)|_{t+\tau} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Following the optimality conditions for differential games with time delays, the Hamiltonian functions for the government and the construction firm are constructed as follows:

$$H_1^D = e^{-\rho t} [\eta E_1(t) + \mu E_2(t) + \pi_1 Q(t) - C_1(t)] + m_1^D(t) [\lambda_1 E_1(t - d_1) + \lambda_2 E_2(t - d_2) - \delta G(t)] \quad (7)$$

$$H_2^D = e^{-\rho t} [\pi_2 Q(t) - C_2(t)] + m_2^D(t) [\lambda_1 E_1(t - d_1) + \lambda_2 E_2(t - d_2) - \delta G(t)] \quad (8)$$

E_1^{D*} and E_2^{D*} can be solved. For G^{D*} , since the delay times for the construction efforts of the government and the construction firm are not necessarily the same, three cases exist: $d_1 < d_2$, $d_1 > d_2$, or $d_1 = d_2$. After solving piecewise and then substituting E_1^{D*} and E_2^{D*} into equation (2) in the manuscript, we can obtain G^{D*} , the solution to the delayed differential equation for the construction firm's goodwill.

The discount factor $e^{-\rho d_i}$ appearing in each player's equilibrium effort reflects the time-value erosion caused by the delay between effort deployment and its goodwill payoff: the longer the delay, the smaller the present-value return on effort invested through the goodwill channel. This mechanism is formalized through the Hamiltonian approach, where each player's effort cost is incurred immediately but the corresponding goodwill contribution materializes only after d_i periods, discounted at rate ρ . In emergency construction, efforts such as resource mobilization (by the firm) or administrative authorization (by the government) produce tangible public recognition only after a lag of d_i periods. The longer the delay, the greater the discount on the expected goodwill return, which reduces the player's marginal incentive to invest

effort. This is consistent with the comparative statics in Corollary 5, which shows $\partial E_i^*/\partial d_i < 0$: as delay increases, the present-value incentive to invest in goodwill diminishes and equilibrium effort falls. In essence, the delay effect functions as an endogenous “tax” on the goodwill channel of effort motivation — longer delays impose a heavier “tax” and thereby weaken the collaborative incentive structure.

Proof of Proposition 2

Similar to Proof of Proposition 1, we construct the Hamiltonian functions for the government and the construction firm:

$$H_1^S = e^{-\rho t} [\eta E_1(t) + \mu E_2(t) + \pi_1 Q(t) - C_1(t) - \varphi C_2(t)] + m_1^S(t) [\lambda_1 E_1(t - d_1) + \lambda_2 E_2(t - d_2) - \delta G(t)] \quad (9)$$

$$H_2^S = e^{-\rho t} [\pi_2 Q(t) - (1 - \varphi) C_2(t)] + m_2^S(t) [\lambda_1 E_1(t - d_1) + \lambda_2 E_2(t - d_2) - \delta G(t)] \quad (10)$$

By solving E_1^{S*} and E_2^{S*} and substituting them into equation (2) in the manuscript, we can obtain G^{S*} for different delay times.

Proof of Proposition 3

Similar to Proof of Proposition 1, we construct the joint Hamiltonian function for the centralized decision-maker:

$$H^C = e^{-\rho t} [\eta E_1(t) + \mu E_2(t) + (\pi_1 + \pi_2) Q(t) - C_1(t) - C_2(t)] + m_C(t) [\lambda_1 E_1(t - d_1) + \lambda_2 E_2(t - d_2) - \delta G(t)] \quad (11)$$

By solving E_1^{C*} and E_2^{C*} and substituting them into equation (2) in the manuscript, we can obtain G^{C*} for different delay times.

S3. Expert interview details

To validate the model assumptions and calibrate key parameter ranges, we conducted semi-structured interviews with five domain experts.

The five experts were recruited through purposive sampling via professional networks and existing research collaborations, targeting individuals with direct involvement or scholarly expertise in emergency construction projects in China. Table S2 summarizes the panel composition.

The interviews were conducted in a semi-structured format, each lasting approximately 60–90 minutes. The interview protocol covered four core themes: (1) the validity of model assumptions, particularly the goodwill dynamics, effort–demand relationships, and delay mechanisms; (2) the real-world mapping of the three decision-making approaches (decentralized, cost-sharing, and centralized) to actual emergency construction practices; (3) practical scenarios illustrating the manifestation of delay effects in emergency construction projects; and (4) the reasonableness of parameter ranges for the numerical simulation.

Table S2: Expert panel composition

ID	Role	Affiliation and background	Experience
E1	Government Official	Government department, overseeing construction procurement; participated in emergency construction projects in Shanghai	10 years
E2	Chief Engineer	State-owned construction enterprise, responsible for commercial operations	15 years
E3	Professor	University, specializing in emergency construction management	22 years
E4	Professor	University, specializing in emergency construction management	18 years
E5	Associate Professor	University, specializing in emergency construction management	12 years